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dynamic corrector and multichannel system of measurements and processing of AE signals are the basis for determining the set of developed algorithms and programs that ensure the execution of signal restoration operations at high speed.

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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN MODERN INFORMATION-MEASUREMENT AND CONTROL SYSTEMS

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Abstract: *The article is dedicated to the increasingly relevant topic of artificial intelligence and its application in information-measurement and control systems. It explores the types of artificial intelligence, its fields of application, and related challenges, and presents issues that can potentially be successfully addressed. The areas of application in information-measurement systems, control systems, including metrology, as well as the advantages gained and the problems encountered during implementation, are discussed.*

The role, tasks, and advantages of AI in enhancing measurement accuracy through big data and artificial neural networks, achieving system adaptability, and enabling prompt decision-making in control systems are examined. The article also addresses existing and potential challenges in achieving high-performance outcomes. The possibilities and advantages of applying AI in metrology are presented. Furthermore, the issues that need to be resolved to qualitatively improve and accelerate the implementation of AI are outlined. The benefits of AI applications in the fuel and energy sector, transportation management, medical fields, and biomedical engineering are particularly emphasized.

Key words: *Artificial intelligence, Information-measurement system, control system, metrology, measurement accuracy, automatic calibration*

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI), which is currently being successfully applied in various fields, plays a crucial role by introducing changes that enable achieving high results in the development of modern equipment and technologies. The role of AI is increasingly growing in information-measurement systems (IMCS) and control systems (CS), especially in technically, technologically, and non-technically important areas such as fuel-energy, medicine, business, transportation management, education, etc. AI plays an important role in automating processes, making prompt decisions based on relevant information, processing Big Data according to various characteristic parameters and features obtained by these systems, improving measurement accuracy, and optimizing control processes. Most companies that prioritize modern equipment and technologies are already showing special interest in the application of AI, placing importance on mastering tools that enable the implementation of necessary solutions. For this reason, it is expected and predicted that AI technology will provide significant income and advantages in the mentioned and other fields in the near future, and thus, the application of AI in IMCS and CS is anticipated to expand at an even faster rate each year [1].

Types and Basic Principles of Artificial Intelligence

If we take a general approach to applied Artificial Intelligence, it can be categorized into several types based on its intellectual capabilities (Figure 1)[2]. Currently, the only existing type of AI is Narrow AI (Weak AI). Although these systems are designed to perform only specific, limited tasks, they can surpass humans in their respective application areas and enable high speed and accuracy.

Figure 1. Categories of AI according to intellectual capabilities

General AI (AGI, Strong AI) is a system that, based on theory, can learn complex intellectual functions according to application areas and replicate them as needed.

The third stage, known as Super AI, is theoretically predicted to be a highly advanced form of AI capable of demonstrating performance based on emotions and consciousness similar to human intelligence.

The fundamental principles of artificial intelligence are based on machine learning and, in particular, deep learning methods (Figure 2) [3-4].

Fig.2. Artificial intelligence in terms of machine learning and deep learning

Machine learning algorithms enable decision-making and predicting by learning patterns from large datasets. Deep learning models, based on artificial neural networks, use a data processing principle analogous to the human brain and allow systems to learn how to perform tasks independently without human intervention. Thus, thanks to such algorithms, artificial intelligence (AI) makes it possible to develop systems that make real-time decisions, improve their performance, and automate complex processes. Modern AI integrates the application of the aforementioned algorithms and approaches, such as expert systems, logical decision-making, and search algorithms, with core principles like statistical learning and pattern recognition. This integration allows AI to function as an “intelligent” system when applied in IMCS and CS[5].

Current problems in IMCS and CS and the solutions offered by AI.

Modern information-measurement and control systems face a number of challenges. First and foremost, there is the problem of processing large volumes of data, the amount of data collected from sensors, devices, and processes is rapidly increasing, making real-time analysis difficult with traditional methods.

Increasing the accuracy of measurements and the system’s automatic adaptation to changing internal and external factors are of particular importance for making correct decisions.

At the same time, the application of effective management in the fuel-energy sector and other areas to reduce losses, optimize economically, and ensure high service quality is also highly relevant.

Innovative approaches can be achieved through the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to solve all these mentioned and similar issues. Since AI algorithms have the ability to rapidly analyze large volumes of data, they allow for the identification of complex patterns that humans may find difficult to detect, enabling timely decision-making.

For example, in the field of energy production and distribution, smart grids, through AI, enable the analysis of real-time data, allowing for dynamic regulation of energy distribution. This makes it possible to minimize transmission losses and increase overall efficiency. At the same time, AI can predict load patterns in the electricity grid and optimize distribution, reducing transmission losses while also enhancing the system’s reliability [6].

Additionally, AI solves traffic congestion problems in smart transportation control systems by optimizing traffic flow on complex routes in real-time and efficiently carrying out effective freight logistics.

For increasing productivity and making automatic operational decisions, AI-based control systems for manufacturing processes analyze the data obtained at all stages of the technological

process, enabling the automatic adjustment of equipment and maintaining process parameters at the required levels.

When it comes to the application of artificial intelligence in the field of medicine, its capabilities in management and diagnostics are especially emphasized. In AI-based control systems, the condition of medical equipment is continuously monitored, allowing for early detection of potential malfunctions. Additionally, AI can analyze patients' vital signs and promptly alert medical professionals in critical situations.

The presented application areas reflect the existing problems of IMCS and CS, as well as how these problems can be addressed through Artificial Intelligence (AI). With the abundance of data, decision-making becomes easier, systems operate more accurately and efficiently, and thanks to the integration of intelligence, new capabilities emerge within these systems.

Processing, predictive analysis and optimization of Data

One of the greatest advantages of applying Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Information-Measurement Systems (IMS) is the effective processing of numerous sensor data collected in large databases. Using machine learning algorithms, the system analyzes data obtained from sensors and measurement devices to learn the normal behavior patterns of the process and automatically detect any deviations. For example, analyzing vibration signals from vibrosensors with AI allows for early detection of mechanical faults in equipment. At the same time, processing camera images is used for quality control, enabling timely identification of defective products during the production process [7].

Thanks to such predictive analytics, enterprises can take preventive measures before equipment failures occur. In addition, AI enables the rapid processing of large volumes of data, creating new opportunities for process optimization. For example, in manufacturing enterprises, AI modules can simultaneously analyze data from dozens of sensors and provide recommendations. In the fields of logistics and supply chain management, AI analysis tools optimize supply routes and inventory distribution based on data, resulting in shorter delivery times and reduced costs. By using an AI-based analytical platform, an industrial enterprise can monitor and optimize the energy consumption of production equipment in real time, allowing it to reduce energy usage per unit of product[8]. Artificial intelligence-based intelligent transport control systems allow for optimal regulation and safety of traffic on various designated traffic lines.

AI also enables automated decision-making in complex control systems. Thanks to its capabilities in data processing and predicting, an AI-based control system not only detects deviations from normal processes but also facilitates optimal control. Thus, through the data processing and predictive analytics capabilities of AI in Information-Measurement Systems (IMCS) and Control Systems (CS), unstable processes are stabilized, the operational life of equipment is extended, the risk of failures is reduced, and overall system efficiency is increased.

Artificial intelligence in metrology

Since metrology is defined as the science of measurement, artificial intelligence offers broad opportunities in this field[9-10]. To ensure high accuracy and reliability in measurements, AI-based systems are used both to improve the performance of measuring instruments and to analyze the results of the measurement process (see Fig. 3)

The application of AI for the automatic calibration of measuring instruments, so-called intelligent calibration systems, can be evaluated by their ability to compare the device's displayed values with normative values, analyze existing errors through machine learning, and automatically adjust the instrument's parameters. As a result, the calibration of measuring instruments can be

carried out more frequently and accurately, leading to a reduction in the percentage of errors in measurements.

AI-based measurement systems are of particular importance due to their capabilities in processing measurement results and predicting errors. Large volumes of data collected from complex measurement systems (such as multi-sensor measurement systems) are analyzed by AI to identify variations and deviations in the measurement process. These capabilities of AI-based systems help reduce measurement uncertainty and improve the accuracy of results, thereby enabling the optimization of the measurement process.

Fig.3. Application of Artificial Intelligence in Metrology

In the field of automated product quality monitoring, AI vision technologies are widely used. Through the analysis of images captured by cameras using AI algorithms, the dimensions and other characteristics of products are rapidly inspected for compliance with standards. For example, an AI system that analyzes camera images of parts moving along a production line can determine in real time whether they meet the required dimensional tolerances. This approach is more efficient than traditional selective testing methods, as each individual product unit is evaluated immediately and independently.

Optimization of sensor networks through AI is also of particular importance. In networks composed of numerous sensors installed for environmental monitoring, AI algorithms process the data to learn which sensors provide more critical information under specific conditions. This enables optimal use of the network's resources (such as energy, transmission bandwidth, etc.). This method not only increases the efficiency of measurements but also reduces the volume of redundant data.

Artificial intelligence introduces a new level in metrology in the field of automatic defect detection. Minor defects and measurement errors, which are difficult to detect using traditional methods, can be identified with greater accuracy by AI. Experiments show that the accuracy of AI-based defect detection systems is significantly higher compared to classical human inspection or simple algorithmic methods. For instance, microscopic cracks or voids in images obtained from industrial X-ray measurements, often missed by experienced specialists, can be reliably detected

by a trained neural network. Such technologies minimize all factors that affect the outcome of measurements, such as device errors and human mistakes, thereby significantly increasing the accuracy, efficiency, and reliability of measurements. Thus, the application of AI in the field of metrology can be considered a new stage in measurement science and contributes to improving the quality of measurements both in industry and scientific research.

Difficulties and Integration Challenges

Although high results are expected from the application of artificial intelligence (AI) in both the IMCS and CSs, it is inevitable that it will face a number of challenges and obstacles. It should be particularly noted that integration with existing systems is a complex process, and adding a new AI module to traditional control infrastructure may cause technical (platform compatibility, data formats, real-time requirements, etc.) and organizational (process restructuring) problems. Specifically, the application of AI in outdated systems often requires significant modernization of those systems. Another key issue is related to personnel training and cultural-institutional adaptation. To effectively use AI-based systems, staff need to understand the new tools and algorithms, and they must undergo training to work with them. In many cases, companies must improve the qualifications of their workforce to implement AI and sometimes make changes to the organizational structure.

Another critical aspect in the application of AI is information security and ethical issues. AI systems typically collect and process large volumes of data, which raises the issue of protecting confidential or sensitive information. For example, if an AI algorithm in an industrial control system continuously exchanges data over a network to monitor process parameters, this data can be intercepted or altered if cybersecurity is weak. This could potentially lead to dangerous situations. At the same time, the explainability and ethics of AI decisions are also important: if it is not clear on what basis an AI system makes a critical control decision, it becomes a kind of “black box” for human experts. This can create trust issues and complicate the allocation of responsibility in the event of an accident.

International research and surveys confirm that a significant number of organizations face challenges when integrating AI. This indicates that implementing AI is not only a technological issue but also a complex transformation in terms of organizational environment. The main goal is for organizations to successfully integrate AI into their existing workflows, which requires proper strategic planning, pilot testing, workforce training, and the establishment of a reliable information technology infrastructure. In addition, it is essential to verify the accuracy and fairness of AI systems (e.g., to prevent biased decisions) and to have risk management plans in place for failure scenarios. Despite these challenges, companies and research institutions are developing strategies to overcome these obstacles, as the potential benefits of AI outweigh the resources required to address these issues.

Future Prospects and Development Directions in the Application of AI

The future of integrating artificial intelligence into information-measurement and control systems is very promising. First and foremost, the development of new algorithms and technologies is ongoing, advancements in machine learning, more efficient neural network architectures, and hybrid model approaches for decision-making will expand the capabilities of AI systems. Even today, researchers are working on models that can learn from less data, methods for Explainable AI, and highly autonomous decision-making systems, all of which could soon become integral parts of information-measurement and control systems (IMCS and CS).

Another key direction is the enhancement and increasing accessibility of computational resources. The development of cloud computing, edge computing, and even quantum computing

technologies will enable faster and more large-scale implementation of AI algorithms. High computational power will simplify real-time processing requirements, allowing the seamless integration of more complex AI models into information-measurement and control systems (IMCS and CS).

Additionally, the volume and quality of data are continuously increasing: due to the spread of Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies, the scale of data collected from various processes is growing exponentially, creating a richer flow of information. This abundance of data serves as “fuel” for AI, more and higher-quality data enables the training of more accurate and reliable models.

At the same time, an important issue is the increasing interest and investments in AI at both the business and government levels. Companies are making significant investments in AI to maintain their competitive edge, while governments are adopting national strategies to promote research and innovation in this field. This trend indicates that most newly established information-measurement systems will almost certainly be designed with AI components integrated. In other words, the future information-measurement systems (IMCS) will become the default “smart” standard.

Several specific directions stand out when looking to the future. Self-learning and self-regulating systems, that is, information-measurement and control systems (IMCS) that adapt their operation based on insights gained from experience accumulated during their functioning, are already at the center of research. Such systems could gradually learn more optimal ways of functioning over time with minimal human intervention.

Further development of predictive analytics and control is another key direction, meaning that AI will not only be used to predict failures but also to proactively optimize the future course of processes. It is expected that future information-measurement and control systems (IMCS and CS) will be able to predict emergencies or performance drops before they occur and take preventive actions accordingly. Finally, the integration of AI with other advanced technologies will open up new possibilities. This includes integration with blockchain technology (for example, to ensure immutable and traceable recording of measurement results) and synergy with the Internet of Things (IoT), where AI operates in a distributed manner using edge computing across a network of smart devices. Such multidisciplinary integration will enable measurement and control systems to become more reliable, transparent, and adaptive.

The aforementioned prospects indicate that the full integration of AI into information-measurement and control systems (IMCS and CS) is an integral part of the “Industry 4.0” and “Industry 5.0” concepts. In the future, companies will have the opportunity to use AI alongside technologies such as digital twins to create virtual models of complex systems, conduct tests on them, and optimize the operation of real systems. At the same time, more intelligent interfaces (e.g., voice assistants, systems supported by augmented reality) will emerge for users, making interaction with IMCS and CS easier. Research and developments in all these directions will increasingly strengthen the role of AI, and within the next decade, current systems will be elevated to an entirely new level.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be stated that artificial intelligence plays a crucial role in enhancing the efficiency and functionality of modern information-measurement and control systems (IMCS and CS). The analysis and examples show that through the active application of AI, companies can optimize processes, reduce costs, and improve the quality of products and services. AI acts as a success factor in the digital economy and holds strategic significance in maintaining competitive

advantage. Therefore, proactive steps by both industry and scientific communities to integrate AI into IMCS and CS can be considered critical decisions in today's world. The outcome will enable the activation of a process that, alongside technological innovation, requires organizational and cultural change in intelligent control.

The application of artificial intelligence in information-measurement systems and metrology opens up unparalleled opportunities to enhance the accuracy, efficiency, and reliability of measurements.

Thanks to automatic calibration, smart sensor networks, and other AI applications, measurement processes are conducted more quickly and accurately. The application of AI in control systems ensures optimal decision-making in real time, reducing the workload on human operators and increasing the adaptability of systems.

Therefore, to fully leverage the potential of AI, further research and development in its application areas are essential. Investments in the improvement of algorithms, the formation of ethical and legal frameworks, and workforce training must continue with special attention to this field. In general, the application of artificial intelligence in modern IMCS and CS marks the beginning of a new era at the intersection of information technology and engineering. In this era, intelligent systems complement human labor, work alongside it, and learn from it.

Additionally, it is important to manage and guide the transformations brought by AI properly to fully harness its potential. Achieving success in this field requires joint efforts from both the scientific community and industry. In this way, AI's potential will transform into successful outcomes, ensuring that the future generations of information-measurement and control systems are highly intellectual.

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